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**AGROBIOLOGICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF
TOMATO(SOLANUM LYCOPERSICUM).**

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***Abstract.** This article presents the results of the study of the agrobiological and technological characteristics of tomato varieties and hybrids. In addition, the research was conducted to study the biological characteristics of the growth and development of tomato plants and the dynamics of the product arriving at the drying area. It mainly focused on the ripening period of tomatoes, the size of the fruit, the productivity of raw materials, technical maturity indicators, and their suitability for drying. According to the results of the study, the average yield in 2022-2024 differed slightly from each other by variant, but this year, compared to the control, Yusuf F1 was 50.0 t/ha. Of the other varieties studied, TMK-22 was 42.0 t/ha, Lodjayn F1 -39.0 t/ha, Burxon F1 - 38.0 t/ha. The lowest average yield in these years was Madera - 35.0 t/ha. Based on the results of the experiment in 2022-2024, a significant difference was observed in the yield of tomato varieties and the amount of fruits suitable for drying. The Yusuf F1 and Burxon F1 varieties stand out as the most productive varieties in terms of yield and quality*

indicators. The total yield of the Yusuf F1 variety was 50.0 t/ha, and the amount of fully ripe fruits was 48.2 t/ha or 96.5%. This indicator confirms the high marketability of the variety and its suitability for drying. At the same time, the amount of fruits suitable for drying was 46.8 t/ha, which is one of the highest results.

Keywords: *variety, hybrid, productivity, phenology, ripening period, technical maturity, raw material, usable, unusable, drying, storage.*

1. Introduction.

Today, the main task is to satisfy the need for fruits and vegetables, taking into account population growth, as well as to provide the processing industry with raw materials. In this regard, one of the important tasks for specialists in this field is to increase the range of dried products in order to fully satisfy this need of the population not only in season, but also throughout the year. The largest share of the annual gross volume of tomato production in the world falls on China - 974 thousand hectares (67.6 million tons), India - 520 thousand hectares (21.2 million tons), Turkey - 225 thousand hectares (13.1 million tons), the USA - 177 thousand hectares (10.5 million tons), Italy (6.6 million tons), Egypt (6.2 million tons), Spain (4.7 million tons), Russia (3.1 million tons). In this regard, Uzbekistan ranks 14th in the world, producing 2.3 million tons of tomatoes per year.

In recent years, tomatoes have been grown on an average of about 70 thousand hectares in Uzbekistan, with a yield of 35-40 tons per hectare. This means that the average per capita production of our country is about 70-80 kg, which indicates that our people have more than enough for their consumption. In this regard, it is necessary to process and store the excess tomato crop. As a result, this is of great importance in bringing additional economic benefits to the country. One of the important areas of processing is the drying and preservation of fruits and vegetables.

Today, the production of dried fruits and vegetables is one of the important directions in the development of agro-industrial enterprises in our country. The production of dried fruits and vegetables is usually associated with the shortness of the season and the characteristics of varieties and hybrids. According to world statistics, in

most countries, losses of up to 30-35% of the harvested tomato crop are observed during the harvesting and storage processes. This shows that the proper use of various drying methods and packaging of the grown tomatoes in various ways prevents this excessive loss.

Today, one of the most promising methods of preserving tomatoes is drying them. In Uzbekistan, this method has become quite popular in recent years. During drying, by dehydrating the raw material, its weight is significantly reduced, its volume decreases, and as a result, the storage process becomes more convenient and easier. Tomatoes are dried mainly in the sun in our conditions. In countries with few sunny days, they are often dried in various electric dryers. Tomatoes are dried mainly whole, cut into equal halves, or in various pieces. Dried tomatoes are stored in packages. The use of dried tomatoes in the world food industry is very widespread, and they are used to prepare powders that are added to food or spices.

Another important feature of tomatoes is their richness in vitamin C. Tomatoes are distinguished by their high nutritional, taste and dietary qualities. Tomatoes are an excellent source of vitamin C (30-35 mg). In addition, tomatoes contain vitamins B1 (aneurin), B2 (riboflavin), B3 (pantothenic acid), PP (nicotinic acid), provitamin A (carotene), potassium, sodium, calcium, magnesium, phosphorus salts, as well as iron, iodine and other beneficial substances. The greatest value in dried tomatoes is represented by ascorbic acid and lycopene, which, in addition to antioxidant properties, have therapeutic and prophylactic properties.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5388 dated March 29, 2018 “On additional measures for the accelerated development of fruit and vegetable growing in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, No. PP-3978 dated October 10, 2018 “On additional measures to increase the efficiency of exporting fruit and vegetable products to foreign markets”, and Resolution No. PP-57 dated February 14, 2025 are aimed at fulfilling the tasks set out in regulatory legal acts aimed at the development of this sector.

2. Object and methods of research.

The objects of research were selected as the medium-ripening varieties of tomatoes zoned in Uzbekistan: Uzbekistan (control), Madera, Novichok, TMK-22, as well as hybrid samples of Yusuf F₁, Burxon F₁, Lodjayn F₁. In these studies, the agrobiological and technological characteristics of the above-mentioned tomato varieties and hybrids were studied. The studies were conducted to study the biological characteristics of the growth and development of tomato plants and the dynamics of the arrival of the product to the drying area. To achieve the set goals, field experiments were conducted in cooperation with farms operating in the Tashkent region and engaged in vegetable growing. The main studies were conducted on the ripening period of tomatoes, the size of the fruit, the productivity of raw materials, technical maturity indicators, and their suitability and unsuitability for drying. In particular, during the experiment, the agrotechnological characteristics of tomatoes were studied and the physical and chemical processes occurring during their drying were studied, taking into account the dependence of the product on the environmental factors of the region in which it is grown.

Usually, the dynamics of growth processes occurring in all plants is assessed by the onset of phenological stages throughout the growing season. Based on the data obtained from phenological observations, the ripening of hybrids and the individual characteristics of their development are considered. Usually, varieties and hybrids are selected with the aim of obtaining tomorrow's product as soon as possible. Then, as soon as the fastest ripening varieties and hybrids are harvested, the technical ripening of the most late-ripening varieties and hybrids begins. The downside of this approach to creating a "green conveyor" is the limited availability of new products in terms of terms, and due to the extended start of the technical maturity phase, the production of many varieties and hybrids may also become a risk of high production burden, i.e. the "start of technical maturity" phases of one variety and hybrid may coincide with the harvest phase of another, much later variety and hybrid.

Another approach to organizing the arrival of tomato fruits by conveyor method is to choose the timing of sowing seeds and planting seedlings in open ground. The advantage of this approach is the use of a single variety with known consumer qualities, and the possibility of pre-establishing sales channels based on the characteristics of the variety or hybrid. For a number of reasons, it is not recommended to use this approach as an independent and single method. The timing of sowing seeds and planting seedlings in open ground should be chosen only taking into account the characteristics of the varieties and hybrids grown in terms of their ripening time. This is primarily due to the fact that the biological response of plants to certain environmental conditions is limited to the "variety" response. For example, the response of early-ripening tomato hybrids to a decrease in day length in the second half of summer is manifested in the formation of flowering shoots, bypassing the stage of formation of the productive organ - the head.

3. Research results.

Below we consider the days from seeding to ripening of tomato varieties and hybrids and their percentages compared to the control. The most important agrobiological characteristic of each variety is its ripening time and the time it takes to reach the market. If this process is accelerated, farmers will be able to get more yield and start the drying process earlier.

During the experiments, one of the important agrobiological characteristics of the varieties studied in the selection of tomato varieties suitable for drying was the observation of the raw material during the vegetation period, that is, from planting to ripening. According to the results of the experiments, the ripening periods of tomato varieties were 120-126 days for the Uzbekistan (control) variety, 90-100 days for the Yusuf F₁ hybrid, 85-95 days for the Burxon F₁ hybrid, 115-120 days for the TMK-22 variety, 97-105 days for the Madera variety, 110-115 days for the Lodjayn F₁ hybrid, and 114-127 days for the Novichok variety. It was also observed in the Burxon F₁ (90 days) and Yusuf F₁ (95 days) hybrids, which are distinguished by the shortest ripening period among tomato varieties and hybrids suitable for drying (see Table 1).

Agrobiological characteristics of tomato varieties and hybrids
(2022-2024)

Varieties and hybrids	Days from sowing to ripening			Average over the years, day	Relative to control, %
	2022	2023	2024		
Uzbekistan (control)	124	126	120	123	100
Yusuf F ₁	90	95	100	95	77,2
Burxon F ₁	85	90	95	90	73,1
TMK-22	120	118	115	118	95,9
Madera	105	97	100	101	82,1
Lodjayn F ₁	110	115	112	112	91,0
Novichok	127	114	120	120	97,5
least difference ₀₅				0,3	
P _%				0,6	

The table above shows the days from sowing to ripening of tomato varieties. This parameter is the main indicator of agrobiological characteristics, which indicates the growth and development rate of the variety. Based on these figures, it is possible to assess the economic and agrotechnical efficiency of each variety. According to the results of the study on ripening dates, the Uzbekistan (control) variety had 123. Since this variety was taken as a control, when comparing it with other varieties and hybrids, it was observed that Yusuf F₁ ripened 95 days, 28 days earlier than the control, Burxon F₁ 90 days, 33 days earlier, TMK-22 - 118 days, 5 days earlier, Madera variety - 101 days, 22 days earlier, Lodjayn F₁ hybrid - 112 days, 11 days earlier, and Novichok - 120 days, 3 days earlier (see Fig.1).

Figure 1. According to the research results, the ripening periods of tomato varieties and hybrids, days (2022-2024)

According to the results of the above studies, in terms of agrotechnical significance, Yusuf F₁ and Burxon F₁ ripen somewhat earlier than other varieties. This allows you to start the drying season earlier and ensure that the drying season lasts longer and more products are dried. As a result, a small entrepreneur or farmer will have the opportunity to receive additional income. However, although these varieties and hybrids had high agrotechnical results during the research years, they had lower yields than others. The results of the research on the yield and technological characteristics of tomato varieties and hybrids during the years of research are presented in the following tables. We will explain this in the analysis of the following tables. Slightly higher yields were observed in the TMK-22 and Novichok varieties, but we can see that the ripening periods of these varieties are somewhat closer to our Uzbek control variety. However, at the same time, although the fruits of these varieties take a long time to fully ripen, we have achieved a high-quality product.

The tables prepared based on the results of the study show the varieties and hybrids and their percentages compared to the control, which show the relationship between the ripening time and yield of each of them. When analyzing the tables based on the results of the study, the numbers and percentages presented play an important role in helping an entrepreneur or a farmer or farm choose a variety. Because when drying tomatoes, they try to plant drying seedlings depending on whether they ripen early or late. According to them, the Yusuf F₁ and Burxon F₁ hybrids participating in

the study ripen slightly earlier than the control. However, their yield was slightly lower, but their early maturity allows them to be sold at a higher price on the market.

Ripening time and percentages relative to control are important and economically important for farmers. If a variety ripens quickly, it helps farmers to harvest faster and calculate the price. Thus, clarifying the ripening time and percentages relative to control for each variety provides a solid basis for determining the differences between varieties and their agrotechnical characteristics. The results of the study of the growing season, that is, the ripening period of tomato fruit, were tried to clearly show the ripening times of each variety and hybrid through the following graph. By showing the ripening time (days from planting to ripening) of each tomato variety on the graph, we can clearly see what kind of yield each variety has. For example, varieties such as Yusuf F₁ and Burxon F₁ can be fast-growing (i.e., have a shorter ripening period). These varieties ripen quickly, that is, the harvesting process is carried out quickly. Varieties such as Novichok and TMK-22 have longer ripening periods, meaning they take longer to harvest. However, these varieties may be suitable for producing a quality harvest.

The analysis of the dynamics of ripening periods on the graph shows that we can find out which varieties ripen quickly and which varieties take longer to harvest. Therefore, a correct analysis of the graph helps to understand the agrotechnical characteristics of each variety. In particular, during the study and analysis of the gradual change of fast-growing varieties such as Yusuf F₁ or Burxon F₁, it was found that since these hybrids are fast-growing, their ripening period was 90-95 days per year. Thus, due to the fast ripening of these varieties, the harvesting process does not take much time. Fast growth or fast ripening means that the variety has a shortened ripening period, that is, it allows for quick harvesting. For example, if Yusuf F₁ ripens in 95 days, this is 28 days faster than Uzbekistan (control), and this indicator, if given on the graph, clearly shows the speed. Thus, such fast-growing varieties are suitable for the drying process, as their quick ripening ensures a quality harvest.

Comparative analyses of early ripening varieties such as Novichok and TMK-22 show that these varieties usually have a longer ripening period. For example, the ripening period of Novichok is 120-125 days. From this it can be concluded that these varieties, along with their long ripening period, also allow for a high-quality harvest and, as a result, ensure the production of tomatoes suitable for drying. If we pay attention to the figure below, we can see that varieties such as TMK-22 have a long ripening period and require a long time to ripen.

In the first year of the study, 2022, the same yield as the control Uzbekistan (control) was Yusuf F₁– 49.0 t/ha. Among the other varieties studied, TMK-22 yielded 40.0 t/ha, Burxon F₁ 39.0 t/ha, and Lodjayn F₁ 38.0 t/ha. The lowest average yield in the same year was Madera 32.0 t/ha.

In the second year of the study year, i.e. 2023, the yield by variants was slightly higher, but this year, compared to the control, Yusuf F₁ was 51.0 t/ha. Among the other studied varieties, TMK-22 was 44.0 t/ha, Madera was 38.0 t/ha, and Lodjayn F₁ was 40.0 t/ha. The lowest average yield this year was Burxon F₁- 37.0 t/ha.

In the third year of the study year, i.e. 2024, the yield by variants differed somewhat between varieties and hybrids, but this year, compared to the control, Yusuf F₁ was 50.0 t/ha. Among the other studied varieties, TMK-22 was 44.0 t/ha, Madera was 38.0 t/ha, and Lodjayn F₁ was 40.0 t/ha. This year, the average lowest yield was Burxon F₁- 37.0 t/ha.

According to the results of the three-year study, that is, in 2022-2024, the average yield by variant differed somewhat from each other, but this year, compared to the control, Yusuf F₁- was 50.0 t/ha. Among the other varieties studied, TMK-22 - 42.0 t/ha, Lodjayn F₁ - 39.0 t/ha, Burxon F₁ - 38.0 t/ha. The average lowest yield in these years was Madera - 35.0 t/ha (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Yield of tomato varieties and hybrids in the study years, t/ha (2022-2024)

The data in the figure above show that the lowest total yield compared to Uzbekistan (control) was recorded in the Madera variety, 72.9%. Only one Yusuf F₁ hybrid had 104.2.

When determining tomato varieties and hybrids suitable for drying, when analyzing their raw material productivity from their total productivity, the highest raw material productivity was observed in the Yusuf F₁ (96.5) and Burxon F₁ (95.0) hybrids on average over the years. Of the tomato varieties and hybrids participating in the observation, the lowest raw material productivity, that is, the indicator of tomatoes suitable for drying, was observed in the Uzbekistan (control) variety (see Table 2).

According to the analysis of the table above, based on the results of the experiment in 2022–2024, a significant difference was observed in the yield of tomato varieties and the amount of fruits suitable for drying. The Yusuf F₁ and Burxon F₁ varieties stand out as the most productive varieties in terms of yield and quality indicators. The total yield of the Yusuf F₁ variety was 50.0 t/ha, and the amount of fully ripe fruits was 48.2 t/ha or 96.5%. This indicator confirms the high marketability of the variety and its suitability for drying. At the same time, the amount of fruits suitable for drying was 46.8 t/ha, which is one of the highest results.

The Burxon F₁ variety also had a total yield of 38.0 t/ha, the amount of fully ripe fruits was 36.1 t/ha (95%), and the amount of fruits suitable for drying was 34.7 t/ha, indicating high productivity. This variety also has a low percentage of unripe fruits (4.5%) and a high quality yield.

Table 2

Average yield and productivity (marketability) of tomato varieties and hybrids participating in the research, t/ha. (2022-2024)

Variety and hybrid samples	Number of selections	Total productivity, t/ha	Fully cooked		Unripe fruits		Fruits suitable for drying	
			t/ha	%	t/ha	%	t/ha	%
Uzbekistan (control)	6	48,0	42±1,2	87,5	6,0±1,2	12,5	36,3±0,6	86,5
Yusuf F ₁	6	50,0	48,2±0,7	96,5	1,8±0,8	3,5	46,8±0,5	97,0
Burxon F ₁	5	38,0	36,1±0,38	95,0	1,8±0,3	4,5	34,7±0,4	96,0
TMK-22	7	42,0	36,8±1,1	87,5	5,2±1,0	12,5	31,8±0,5	86,5
Madera	5	35,0	32,6±1,1	93,0	2,4±1,0	7,0	31,0±0,32	95,0
Lodjayn F ₁	6	39,0	36,0±0,9	92,5	3,0±0,97	7,5	34,2±0,36	95,0
Novichok	4	36,0	32,4±1,8	90,0	3,6±1,8	10	28,4±0,86	87,5
least difference ₀₅			0,9	-	1,0	-	0,1	-
Xs%			3,8	-	4,2	-	4,0	

4. Conclusion

1. The Uzbekistan (control) variety showed good results with a yield of 48.0 t/ha, fully ripe fruits of 42.0 t/ha, and fruits suitable for drying of 36.3 t/ha, but it was found that the new hybrids were superior to them.

2. Although the TMK-22 and Madera varieties also showed good results, they had a slightly higher amount of unripe fruits (5.2 t/ha and 2.4 t/ha, respectively), which may make them less effective for drying.

3. The Novichok variety had a yield of fruits suitable for drying of 28.4 t/ha, which is a lower indicator compared to other varieties. Due to the relatively high standard error (± 0.86), some variability in the results was observed. Therefore, this variety is recommended for mass drying processes with limitations.

4. In general, Yusuf F₁ and Burxon F₁ hybrids are considered suitable for drying due to their high marketability and the proportion of fruits suitable for drying.

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